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Author name(s):	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL), Leidy Vanessa Enriquez Florez (ENoLL)	
Contributor(s):	Despoina Petsani (AUTH), Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL), Teemu Santonen (LAUREA), Paraskevi Giourka (AV), Kim Helsen (LicaLab)	
Reviewer(s):	Tamas Toth (TREBAG)	Panagiotis Bamidis (AUTH)
Approved by:	Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Project Coordinator	
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The **VITALISE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	Belgium
2	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
3	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	LAUREA	Finland
4	THOMAS MORE KEMPEN VZW	LICALAB	Belgium
5	FUNDACION INTRAS	INTRAS	Spain
6	TREBAG SZELLEMI TULAJDON- ES PROJEKTMENEDZSER KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	TREBAG	Hungary
7	ASOCIACION DE INDUSTRIAS DE CONOCIMIENTO Y TECNOLOGIA - GAIA - EUSKALHERRIKO EZAGUTZA ETA TEKNOLOGIA INDUSTRIEN ELKARTEA	GAIA	Spain
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain
9	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	Greece
10	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	AIT	Austria
11	SOCIALIT SOFTWARE E CONSULTING SRL	SIT	Italy
12	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain
13	WITA SRL	WITA	Italy
14	ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC	AV	Bulgaria
15	VILABS OE	VILABS	Greece
16	FORUM DES LIVING LABS EN SANTE ET AUTONOMIE	LLSA	France
17	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT INDHOVEN	TUE	Netherlands
18	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	Canada
19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

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Abbreviations

FTT	Fast Track Training
TA	Transnational Access
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

This document reports on the online and educational materials produced until M18 within the context of Work Package 4 in the VITALISE project. This document is directly related to Task 4.2 “Online educational material and training programmes” which aims to gather all the learning materials produced to disseminate the Living Lab potential to researchers throughout Europe and beyond in the Health & Wellbeing domain.

The educational materials include all the online and printed version of the contents produced by WP4 team within the context of:

- the **first VITALISE Summer School** for young researchers held in Marathon, Greece in July 2022.
- The **first Fast Track Training course** provided for both Virtual and Transnational Access of external researchers in September 2022.
- The **VITALISE Commercialisation Bootcamp** held at the Open Living Days 2022 annual conference in Turin (Italy) in September 2022.
- The **VITALISE panel management and wiki videos** created to promote the Living Lab methodology.
- Links to the learning materials provided from **relevant EU funded projects** in the field.
- **Educational posters:** presenting and explaining the Joint Research Activities explanation and the VITALISE approach to enable open access for research data processing.
- **Two VITALISE Publications:** “Towards a Taxonomy for Health Living Lab Data Collection Devices” and “Harmonizing the Evaluation of Living Labs: A Standardized Evaluation Framework”.

The updated version of this deliverable is expected at the end of the VITALISE project (in M36) and will report on the educational materials produced for the Second VITALISE Summer School in 2023, the updated contents of the Fast Track Training following the other 2 rounds of the VITALISE open calls for Transnational and Virtual Access, the Second VITALISE Commercialisation Bootcamp, as well as the materials that will be created for the VITALISE Postgraduate Course in 2023.

2 Introduction

VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE designs and develops ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE invests in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

This deliverable, as part of the VITALISE project, presents the online and printed educational materials produced for capacity building of European researchers around the Living Labs methodology, within the context of Work Package 4 “Capacity Building and Training”. This WP strives to perform training of new researchers and new Living Labs within the Health & Wellbeing sector, as well as supports the development of the required materials for training and education.

This document offers an overview of the collaborative work produced both in Task 4.2 “*Online educational material and training programmes*”, in collaboration with Task 4.1 “*Organisation of summer schools for young researchers*”, Task 4.4 “*Fast Track Training*” and Task 4.5 “*Design and implementation of common postgraduate courses*”, as it is the result of all the activities performed and the material produced so far for increasing knowledge of VITALISE external researchers through our Capacity Building Programme.

The results presented here are intended to offer a preliminary picture of the starting documentation and materials for the VITALISE training and education, which will be constantly updated and created until the end of the project, and more in detail for the above-mentioned tasks, as well as within the context of Task 3.7 “Panel management tool”, strictly related to the Living Lab methodology for enacting user engagement in the long term for the VITALISE researchers. This document includes both online and printed educational material that has been produced in VITALISE as at this point the differentiation of the two types was not possible.

In fact, the VITALISE educational materials will include at the end of the project information about **Living Lab methodologies and services, the standards produced, and the use of ICT tools produced in WP3** which are currently under development. Moreover, during Task 4.1, we will prepare **informative Living Lab Guidelines for new Living Labs wishing to be aligned with the VITALISE Standards.**

3 VITALISE Educational Materials

In this chapter, we offer the reader a short description of the different VITALISE lines of actions in which the Capacity Building initiatives have been situated within the first year of project development, as well as direct access to the online and printed educational materials included in our website.

3.1 Fast Track Training 2022

VITALISE project grants free **Transnational Access (TA)** to external researchers from multiple disciplines to the project's Living Lab Research Infrastructures. During their stay, a 2-day **fast track training (FTT) program** is provided to immerse them in the world of Living Labs. The program covers diverse topics such as Living Lab introduction and services, The importance of harmonisation, Living Lab methodology, Panel management and how to engage target groups, etc. The fast track training agenda is presented below:

	Day 1 (training block 1-4)	Day 2 (training block 5-8)
09:30-10:30	1. Coffee and welcome, Icebreaker	5. Methodology: Design thinking, co-creation, focus group, human factor study, ...
10:30-11:00	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>
11:00-12:30	2. Meet the colleagues	6. Methodology workshop: (3 options)
12:30-13:30	<i>Lunch</i>	<i>Lunch</i>
13:30-15:00	3. Short intro into LL LL services Ethical framework	7. Panel management – Target groups and how to engage them
14:00-15:30	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>
15:30-16:30	4. Vitalise: The importance of harmonisation	8. Free block E.g. LiCalab: How to deal with companies – business model preparation

Table 1 VITALISE Fast Track Training Agenda

The first two blocks comprise the welcoming part. Both the visiting researchers and the hosting Living Labs will introduce themselves. An icebreaker exercise will help to set the tone. The icebreaker is an animation technique that makes participants more conducive to creativity and sharing. Typically carried out at the start of a meeting, it is an exercise that aims to relax the atmosphere and put the participants in a state of mind of openness necessary for the creative posture.

In the third training block we discover what defines the Living Lab, which roles and actors can be found in the Living Lab context, etc. Living labs can provide different services. Another important topic in this block is the ethical framework which is increasingly important in a continuously changing innovation context. Ethical challenges and how to tackle them can be discussed at the end of this block.

The fourth training block is about the importance of harmonisation, which is the core business of VITALISE. We guide the researchers through the objectives, challenges and different work packages

of the VITALISE project, putting the focus on the different joint research activities to be conducted throughout the project.

The second day starts with a training block regarding methodologies. Starting from a design thinking perspective, different methods and tools are discussed. In the sixth block, theory is put into practice with a methodology workshop. Three options are possible: 1) The hosting Living Lab supports the visiting researchers with further elaboration of their study to be conducted during the TA, 2) the hosting Living Lab demonstrates a method or tool of their choice, or 3) The UX design speed testing template, provided by one of the consortium partners, is used as an example.

The seventh block comprises the issue of panel management and how to engage target groups. The benefit of having a panel database is explained and recruitment strategies are examined.

The final block is a free block to fill in depending on the hosting Living Lab's own expertise or best practices. As an example, a training block on how to deal with companies and business model preparation is included.

Throughout the FTT and TA, a self-reflection diary (NoteTheBook) is available. This is a platform developed specifically within the context of VITALISE by one of the consortium partners (TREBAG). The overarching idea behind the NoteTheBook platform is that interacting with the study material by means of taking notes, highlighting texts, sorting out ideas and concepts, marking paragraphs, rewriting sentences in our own words is one of the most commonly and most effectively used techniques for learning. This type of educational engagement creates focused attention by getting in a real touch with the study material. The platform is available at this link: <https://vitalise.trebag.hu/>. By the end of the TA, researchers will have their own personalised PDF booklet to take home.

The complete set of educational materials prepared for the VITALISE Fast Track Training is also publicly available in the project website [here](#).

3.2 Summer School 2022

The VITALISE Summer School aimed to provide researchers worldwide effective training both on how to implement the Living Lab methodology in their studies, as well as involve Living Labs Research Infrastructures and their services in their Health and Wellbeing research studies.

In total, 18 VITALISE External Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain joined the Summer School 2022 and had the opportunity to learn more about the open innovation and Living Lab tools, methods and services to improve their research and follow new scientific paths thanks to the support of the VITALISE high-experienced trainers on the Living Lab methodology.

Participants were also invited to access the VITALISE ICT tools and infrastructure within the project open calls to collaborate on scientific research with Living Labs recognized and labelled by the European Network of Living Labs.

The VITALISE Summer School was jointly organised and co-located with the [School As Living Labs \(SALL\) / FOODSHIFT Summer School 2022](#).

Outcomes for the VITALISE Summer School participants

Participants to the VITALISE Summer School took advantage from networking and peer to peer learnings with highly experienced trainers from the Living Lab community, as well as created a complete roadmap to develop their research works by implementing the Living Lab methodology, with the support and guidance of the VITALISE trainers.

In terms of educational programme, the VITALISE Summer School included:

- 5 hours in total of expert lecturers.
- 5 hours of hands-on workshops to improve your research.
- 1-hour inspirational interaction with representatives of projects where Living Labs were involved.

Day 1 Living Labs methods & tools for researchers		Trainer/s
09:00 – 10:00 am	Welcome and objective Living Labs basics, benefits and challenges	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL) Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)
10:00 – 11:00 am	How researchers can be involved and use Living Labs in their daily job: case studies	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)
11:00 am – 12:00 pm	Tour de table: get to know each other	Session moderated by Leidy Enriquez (ENoLL)
12:00 – 1:00 pm	Living Labs services for researchers applied to case studies	Teemu Santonen (LAUREA)
1:00 – 2:00 pm	<i>Lunch Break</i>	
2:00 – 4:00 pm	Hands on exercise on selected methods & services for small research design and peer to peer learning	Session moderated by Teemu Santonen (LAUREA)

Day 2 Co-creating with Living Labs to improve your research		Trainer/s
10:00 – 11:00 am	IPRs and owners of the data within Living Labs	Alexandra Anagnostopoulou (AUTH)
11:00 am – 12:00 pm	Experimentation & co-creation in a real-life environment	Beatriz Merino (UPM)
12:00 – 1:00 pm	Hands on exercise: co-creation session on your selected research cases	Session moderated by Beatriz Merino (UPM)
1:00 – 2:00 pm	Lunch Break	
2:00 – 3:00 pm	How to improve your research through Living Labs	Eva Kehayia (McGill)
3:00 – 4:00 pm	Inspirational session with representatives from research projects where living labs were included	Antonid Billis, LifeChamps project Despoina Mantziari, URBANOME project Annita Varela, InAdvance project
4:00 – 5:00 pm	Joint SALL & VITALISE Summer School Workshop	Workshop facilitators: Leidy Enriquez (ENoLL) Despoina Petsani (AUTH)

Table 2 First VITALISE Summer School Agenda

All the educational materials produced and provided during the Summer School 2022 are available on the project website at this [link](#). This includes a set of PowerPoint slides and documents focusing on the following contents:

- Introduction to the Summer School.
- Living Labs basics, benefits and challenges.
- How researchers can be involved and use Living Labs in their daily job: case studies.
- Living lab innovation process and tools.
- Improving my research through Living Labs.
- Experimentation and co-creation in a real-life environment.
- Data management and ownership within Living Labs.
- Data ownership within Living Labs.
- Protocol for ethics.
- Protocol examples.

3.3 Bootcamp 2022

The VITALISE Bootcamp focuses on how to exploit research results and turn them into a product or service. VITALISE uses practical tool - specially adapted for Living Lab-based research - to judge the innovation potential of research elements. Basic principles of business building, strategy and tactics for commercialization, and appropriate paths to market were also be covered. Real-life start-up case studies were used to illustrate the various factors involved in taking a research product into the market.

Profile: The bootcamp was designed for idea owners, coaches, managers, start-ups, and researchers seeking to exploit their research results, with the aim of assessing the innovation readiness and maturity of projects.

Aim of the Bootcamp: The Bootcamp introduced tools (the Innovation Radar and the KTH Innovation Readiness Level TM Model¹) for conducting a reality check and define more objectively the progress of innovative projects towards commercialization.

Learning outcomes:

- How to judge the innovative and commercial potential of research- based results.
- Some basics of commercialization.
- How to apply VITALISE Commercialization framework.
- Real-life commercialization challenges from a research start-up.

Approach: The bootcamp started with familiarizing participants with the Innovation Radar² and KTH Innovation readiness model. It was followed by a hands-on exercise, where participants could watch a demonstration of a start-up case in real-time. Participants were guided through the evaluation process to learn how to assess the maturity and current development status of projects, including those supported by Living Labs. The bootcamp agenda is shown below.

VITALISE Bootcamp 2022		Contributors
16:00 – 16:10 pm	Welcome and objectives	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL) Martina Desole (ENoLL)
16:10 – 17:00 pm	Understand the tactics to commercialize your project	Paraskevi Giourka (AV)

¹ <https://kthinnovationreadinesslevel.com/>

² <https://www.innoradar.eu/>

17:00 17:50 pm	Assess the commercialization potential of your project	Adriane Trash (AV)
17:50 – 18:00 pm	Conclusions and next opportunities from VITALISE Capacity Building Programme	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)

Table 3 First VITALISE Commercialisation Bootcamp agenda

The educational materials prepared for the First VITALISE Commercialisation Bootcamp are available on the project website [here](#).

3.4 Panel Management & Wiki (AUTH)

The Panel Management and VITALISE Harmonization Wiki are two online tools that are offered to Living Labs and external researchers aiming to facilitate the accessibility of Living Lab research infrastructures.

The Panel Management tool (app.thepanelab.com) can facilitate the communication and event scheduling with Living Lab stakeholders. Through the Panel Management tool, researchers can gather information about the Living Lab’s panel, the stakeholders that consist of it, schedule communication, gather the feedback from the communications and promote various events and pilot activities. It is a useful tool for researchers that want to perform research activities in Living Labs. For that reason, we have prepared an educational video that guides the user through the tool and presents the various functionalities. The video can be found [here](#).

Furthermore, the [wiki page](#) is an online tool that presents in an interactive way the VITALISE Standards for Living Labs. The wiki is a collaborative tool in which everyone can insert comments and suggestions about how to improve the existing version of Living Lab Standards. Also, it can be used to access in a convenient way all the information regarding the VITALISE Living Lab Standard. An educational video has been prepared in order to demonstrate how the wiki can be accessed and used in order to allow researchers to interact with it in a convenient and effective way. The video can be found [here](#).

3.5 VITALISE Educational Posters

Two educational posters have been produced by the VITALISE team to be used as printed materials within the VITALISE General Assembly meeting in Helsinki from 11 to 12 May 2022.

The first poster provides information about the VITALISE Joint Research Activities, while the second poster offers a detailed set of information about the VITALISE approach to enable open access for research data processing. The two posters are included below and accessible through the VITALISE website [here](#).

Virtual Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure

Joint Research Activities

The Joint Research Activities (JRAs) bring together researchers from different Living Labs in collaborative projects that lead to joint results, publications and presentations.

Rehabilitation

This JRA aims to gain insight on each Living Lab, in order to harmonise Health & Wellbeing Living Lab infrastructure & procedures in Europe and beyond, in the context of rehabilitation. Secondly, it aims to investigate the potential of innovative technologies for rehabilitation through Living Lab methodologies.

Transitional Care

This study aims to evaluate the feasibility and benefit of collecting multichannel data across Living Labs on the topic of transitional care and to harmonise the data processes and collection. Secondly, it aims to investigate the collection and use of digital biomarkers and explore initial patterns in the data that demonstrate the potential to predict transitions outcomes.

Everyday Living Environments

This JRA aims to co-create and test a harmonised research protocol for developing big data driven hybrid personas, hypothetical user archetypes created to present a user community. Secondly, it aims to study the utilisation & applicability of technologies in various everyday living & living lab environments.

Project coordinator: Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis
Scientific coordinator: Prof. Panos Bamidis

<https://vitalise-project.eu> VITALISE H2020 project
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Figure 1 VITALISE poster on Joint Research Activities

Figure 2 VITALISE poster on our approach to enable open access for research data processing

3.6 VITALISE Publications

VITALISE has produced scientific publications in order to share and disseminate the VITALISE results with researchers and scientific audience. Two publications can be also used as educational material as they present the Taxonomy for Health Living Lab Data Collection Devices and the Living Lab evaluation framework that are important tools for researchers. Both papers were presented at The XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference "Innovating in a Digital World", held in Copenhagen, Denmark on 05 June to 08 June 2022. The publications are presented below:

- Towards a Taxonomy for Health Living Lab Data Collection Devices:** Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain can integrate ICT tools and other technical devices into the research and innovation within this domain. However, there is no systematic understanding what kind of ICT tools and other technical devices are used by Living Labs and how they can be categorized. This study presents the creation of a taxonomy for systematically grouping data and devices used in Living Lab concept, as well as the technical representation framework. The analysis concluded with 8 categories and 63 subcategories

of data that are gathered from Living Labs using various technologies. The taxonomy and the included data model enable Living Lab researchers and customers quickly find what tools they need for their research while supporting open data movement among the Living Labs. The paper is accessible [here](#).

- **Harmonizing the evaluation of Living Labs: a standardized evaluation framework.** Candidate LLs joining LL associations and networks (ENoLL, Forum LLSA, etc.) undergo quality assessment processes based on specific criteria and evaluation frameworks to guarantee members meet their LL standards. Currently, limited attention is paid on how such evaluation methods can contribute to future LL-performance. The need to deeper understand the architectural aspects of LLs and further study effective management-approaches has been raised by other authors. Schuurman (2015) proposed a macro–meso-micro-level approach for classifying LLs. Despite its potential value, this three-level analysis approach has not yet been fully recognized in existing LL evaluation frameworks. The adoption of a harmonized macro-meso-micro evaluation approach, with a clear focus on the macro-level could support the development of LL towards sustainability, impact and efficacy. This paper aims to define a set of harmonized weighted criteria for a comprehensive LL evaluation framework to be used for assessing LLs on all three levels based on multi-method research approaches. The paper is accessible [here](#).

4 Conclusions & Next Steps

This deliverable has presented the online and educational materials produced until M18 within the context of Work Package 4 in the VITALISE project. This document is directly related to Task 4.2 “Online educational material and training programmes” which aims to gather all the learning materials produced to disseminate the Living Lab potential to researchers throughout Europe and beyond in the Health & Wellbeing domain.

This document will be updated in M36 to include the online and printed educational materials created by the VITALISE team within the context of the WP4, such as the Second VITALISE Summer School in 2023, the updated contents of the Fast Track Training following the other 2 rounds of the VITALISE open calls for Transnational and Virtual Access, the Second VITALISE Commercialisation Bootcamp, as well as the materials that will be created for the VITALISE Postgraduate Course in 2023, which is currently under development.